

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Herbivore prevalence poorly predicts yield in diverse cropping systems

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Abstract

1. Industrialized agriculture needs sustainable alternatives to pesticides to avoid negative impacts on the environment and human health. Crop diversification is known to decrease pest pressure in agricultural crops. Up till now, the effects of insect herbivores on crop yield are often assumed to be equal among cropping systems.
2. We sampled the insect community and yield of cabbages in five distinct cropping systems characterized by increasing crop diversity. Using structural equation modelling, we assessed how herbivorous insects influence cabbage yield through direct consumptive effects and indirect effects via changes in the insect community.
3. The most diverse cropping system synergistically increased cabbage yield and herbivorous insect abundance and richness, whereas the other cropping systems did not differ consistently from each other.
4. Cropping systems alter the effect that herbivores have on cabbage crop yield, where more herbivores do not necessarily lead to reduced yields. Specific insects had cropping system-specific effects on yield, which reflect differences in the potential for distinct cropping systems to contribute to biological control of distinct herbivorous insects.
5. In one of the cropping systems with cultivar mixtures, we observed negative impacts of herbivores on cabbage yield. This may result from a companioning cultivar drawing natural enemies away from the main cultivar, which would result in reduced biological control of herbivores on the main cultivar.
6. *Synthesis and applications.* Our study shows that the design and characteristics of cropping systems should be considered when assessing insect herbivory effects on crop yield. As herbivorous insects have a smaller impact on yield in diverse cropping systems, crop diversification may synergize biodiversity conservation and food production.

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agroecosystem, *Brassica*, conservation biological control, crop diversification, herbivorous insects, plant-mediated interaction, strip cropping, structural equation modelling

1 | INTRODUCTION

Current high-input industrialized farming practices are highly productive and thereby contribute to the growing food demand. However, they reduce soil health, biodiversity and pollute (natural) ecosystems (Beaumelle et al., 2023; Wagner et al., 2021). Crop diversification can sustainably maintain crop yield and quality by stimulating ecological processes that replace inputs like chemical fertilizers and pesticides (Rakotomalala et al., 2023; Tamburini et al., 2020). The ecological processes that concertedly determine yield, like crop growth and herbivore pressure, exhibit complex interactions that are highly context dependent. Integrated pest management (IPM) is one of the pillars of the EU Farm to Fork strategy to ensure sustainable food production (European Commission, 2020), and crop diversification is suggested as an important IPM tool to prevent pest outbreaks (Barzman et al., 2015). Therefore, a greater understanding of how crop diversification affects the ecological interactions between herbivorous insects and crops will ultimately contribute to designing sustainable cropping systems that enhance pest control.

Diversified cropping systems can alter herbivore abundances, crop growth, and consequently crop yield and quality. Appropriately designed, diversified cropping systems facilitate beneficial tri-trophic interactions, improve soil health, and enhance crop yield and quality (Beillouin et al., 2021; Carrillo-Reche et al., 2023; Juventia et al., 2021). Reducing the use of chemical fertilizers, shifting to organic alternatives, and including nitrogen-fixing crops in the cropping system alter resource availability (Jensen et al., 2010; Vikeftoft et al., 2021), which increases crop resilience to pests and diseases (Aguilera et al., 2021; Han et al., 2022). Intercropping of structurally dissimilar crops and including semi-natural habitats, like beetle banks and flower strips, enhances natural enemy abundance and performance (Beillouin et al., 2021; Croijmans et al., 2024; Letourneau et al., 2011; Poveda et al., 2008; Rakotomalala et al., 2023). Intercropping systems reduce the apparency or reachability of host plants for herbivores, as neighbouring crops serve as a physical or chemical barrier (Mansion-Vaque et al., 2020). Allowing genotypic variation within crops increases resistance to herbivory (Reiss & Drinkwater, 2018; Tooker & Frank, 2012), and selecting for crop genotypes with complementary traits further increases crop resistance to herbivores and diseases (Barot et al., 2017). Thus, cropping system choices in time (e.g. rotations, relay cropping), space (e.g. crop configurations, field sizes), genetic composition (i.e. composition of crop species, cultivars, varieties; Ditzler et al., 2021) and management (e.g. tillage, pesticide and fertilizer use) affect crop growth, herbivore abundances and yield in a myriad of ways. However, if and how cropping systems alter how

herbivores affect crop yield and quality has rarely been studied, and the effect on yield per herbivore is usually regarded to be similar among cropping systems.

The impact of herbivorous insect pests occurs over the lifetime of crop plants and often involves species-rich communities. Herbivores may affect yield directly by causing crop injury. The effect of herbivores on yield via direct consumption depends on the timing of injury, the capacity of the plant to defend itself and compensate for the damage to tissues and on plant-mediated interactions with other herbivores. Plant growth-defence trade-offs vary with plant ontogeny and determine the direct impact of herbivory on yield (Boege & Marquis, 2005; Zst & Agrawal, 2017). In addition to such direct consumptive interactions, herbivores may indirectly affect crop yield by altering the crop-insect community over the course of the growing season via plant-mediated (multi-trophic) interactions (Mertens et al., 2021; Ohgushi, 2005; Van Zandt & Agrawal, 2004). Herbivore prevalence is affected by plant-mediated legacies of previous herbivore presence, which affects the colonization of crops by new herbivores through, for example changes in plant apparency or the occupation and depletion of specific niches (Ohgushi, 2005; Van Zandt & Agrawal, 2004). Furthermore, herbivory can lead to enhanced plant defences via induced defences throughout the growing season. Plant responses to insect herbivory may directly enhance resistance to subsequent herbivore attacks, and the volatiles released after herbivory may lead to the establishment of beneficial tri-trophic interactions by attracting natural enemies of current and future herbivores (Cuny et al., 2018; Poelman et al., 2023). If injury by early herbivores on non-marketable plant parts leads to reduced herbivory later in the development of the crops or induces an overcompensation response in the plant, then herbivory can even be beneficial for crop yield (Garcia & Eubanks, 2019; Poveda et al., 2010). Which herbivores have the most prominent influence on crop yield and quality is determined by the combination of direct and indirect processes, and these processes are likely affected by the agroecological context in which the crops are grown in.

In this multi-year and location study, we examined the direct consumptive effect and the indirect plant- or community-mediated effects of herbivores on plant growth, fresh harvestable weight, and damage to the crop; and whether these effects are altered in different cropping systems. For this purpose, we examined white cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata*) crop performance in five cropping system treatments: a monoculture and four strip-cropping treatments (Figure 1). First, we tested whether cropping systems affect fresh weight and damage of cabbage heads, and herbivore abundance and richness before and during cabbage head formation (i.e. early- and late season; Juventia et al., 2021). Second, we explored the causal relation between early- and late-season plant size

FIGURE 1 Conceptual representation of experimental set-up and measurements. (a) The five cropping system treatments included in this study. Text below strips indicates what was grown in the strips. In the cropping system with multiple cultivars, these replaced some of the main cultivar plants keeping plant density equal. For the systems with nitrogen-fixing plants (faba bean, pea or clover), these were added to the poaceous crops, increasing plant density. (b) We measured individual plants throughout the growing season. (c) We measured plant diameter and number of leaves throughout the season (1), total wrapper leaf and cabbage head fresh weights after harvest (2) and damage by chewing insects on the cabbage head (3). (d) We counted and identified herbivorous insects and grouped these into four classes: (1) flea beetles, (2) thrips, (3) phloem suckers, and (4) chewing insects. See [Table S2](#) for the species that were classified in each herbivore class.

and fresh harvestable weight, and if cropping system alters this relation. Third, we examined how cropping systems alter the effect of herbivore abundance and richness on fresh harvestable weight and damage, and whether these effects change depending on whether the herbivores are present before or during cabbage head formation. Fourth, since different herbivores might interact in time and space (Mertens et al., 2021), and because herbivores differ markedly in the type and severity of injury caused by their feeding (Boege & Marquis, 2005), we also examined how four different herbivore groups affected fresh harvestable weight and damage, both before and during head formation. We hypothesized that herbivores reduce yield by injuring plants, but that the strength of these effects differs among herbivore groups. Furthermore, we expected that the effect of herbivores on fresh harvestable weight and damage would be reduced in more diverse cropping systems. We discuss how plant growth stage, herbivore community and cropping system interact to alter crop yield and damage. Pest outbreaks of herbivores may be dampened by community interactions serviced by crop diversity that stimulates among others the abundance and diversity of predators. As such, we emphasize how pre-emptively considering herbivorous insects as pests is flawed and limits conservation efforts and sustainable farming practices.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Study area

The relationship between white cabbage cultivation and insect herbivores was studied over three years in two long-term strip-cropping experiments at two different locations in the Netherlands: Wageningen and Lelystad (+/- 60km between the two locations). Both experimental locations were managed organically without the use of biological or chemical pesticides. The fields in Wageningen were located north of the Wageningen University campus (51°59'24" N, 5°39'36" E, 13m a.s.l.), as part of a larger network of experimental fields. The soil type was loamy sand. The surrounding landscape was diverse, with many small experimental fields (<1.5 ha) and semi-natural habitats like tree lines and ditches. The experimental fields were enclosed by other smaller experimental plots of Wageningen University to the south, a small-scale farm to the west, larger experimental fields to the north, and a busy regional road to the east. The fields at Lelystad were located east of the city of Lelystad at the Wageningen Research Field Crops location (52°32'33" N 5°34'23" E, -4 m a.s.l.). The soil type here was sandy clay loam, claimed from the sea in

1957. The surrounding landscape consisted mainly of larger-scale experimental fields (5–10 ha) and large-scale agriculture (10–40 ha), with some small semi-natural habitats throughout the landscape, like small waterways and flower strips.

2.2 | Experimental design

At Wageningen, three main crop pairs were used throughout the three years: white cabbage–wheat, potato–grass and pumpkin–barley (see scientific names in [Table S1](#)). In 2019, sugar beet was attempted instead of pumpkin, but this crop failed to establish, and these strips were left bare that year. Also, in 2021, a switch was made from wheat to oat. At Lelystad, four main crop pairs were grown: white cabbage–wheat, potato–grass, sugar beet–barley and carrot–onion. The crops were chosen in close collaboration with Dutch farmers to ensure crops were relevant in developing strategies for creating more sustainable crop production systems. The focus of this paper is on white cabbage and associated herbivorous insects.

Five different cropping system treatments were established that differed in spatial and genetic diversity and management, but that followed the same crop sequence over time ([Figure 1](#)). One large-scale monoculture of one crop without genetic variation was established for white cabbage on a reference field at both locations. We established four strip treatments: Strip, Strip_cultivar, Strip_additive and Strip_diversity. A single 3-meter-wide strip of white cabbage consisted of four rows of plants, fitting farm operations. The simplest strip treatment included white cabbage and wheat or oat in strips of three meters wide (Strip). Here, each strip only included one crop without genetic variation. In Strip_cultivar, we introduced intraspecific variation by mixing two cultivars within the strips. In Strip_additive, we included legumes within the neighbouring cereal crop and mixtures of endangered arable flora at the edges of the strip (see composition in [Table S1](#)). Lastly, in Strip_diversity, which was only established at Wageningen, we combined the elements of Strip_cultivar and Strip_additive and included all six main crops in strips next to each other. At Wageningen, the Strip_additive and Strip_diversity systems received organic plant fertilizers instead of animal manure. All treatments followed the same crop rotation, and green manures were regularly grown in between two crops in consecutive years.

The treatments were organized in an incomplete block design, as including a monoculture on each field that included all four strip-cropping systems was not feasible due to spatial constraints. Thus, at both locations a reference field was used every year that included a monoculture and the simplest strip treatment (Strip). All strip treatments, including Strip, were placed in a complete block design on three (Wageningen) or two (Lelystad) fields. Within a field, all treatments had three strips per crop, and only the central four strips of each crop pair per treatment were used for measurements, as the outside two strips could have interfered with neighbouring treatments. For a visualization of the field set-up, see [Figure S1](#).

2.3 | Ethics approval

This research was not reviewed by an institutional or governmental regulatory body as the work was performed on invertebrates. All observations were made on Wageningen University and Research grounds and our fieldwork did not need externally granted permissions.

2.4 | Study system

In this agroecological study, we examined the interaction between white cabbage yield and quality and the above-ground community of herbivores that naturally occur on white cabbage and were observable by eye. We did not release any of the observed herbivores.

We used white cabbage cultivar Rivera as the main cash crop cultivar, except at Lelystad in 2021, when it was replaced with a similar cultivar, Expect. In the Strip_cultivar and Strip_diversity treatments, we included a 1/8th replacement of Rivera (or Expect) by cultivar Christmas Drumhead. This cultivar is known to be more attractive to several herbivore species and parasitoids (Croijmans et al., 2022; Croijmans et al., 2024; Poelman, Dam, et al., 2009; Poelman, Oduor, et al., 2009) and was used as a trap crop to lure herbivores and have them culled by natural enemies. Replacement of cabbage cultivars always happened in the central two of four plant rows within the strips, where every fourth Rivera plant was replaced by a Christmas Drumhead plant. The purpose was to maximize the number of Rivera plants that neighboured at least one Christmas Drumhead plant. White cabbage plants were planted at five weeks old, when the wheat or oat had already formed a dense cover. Wheat or oat was harvested halfway through the cabbage growing season and replaced by green manure.

2.5 | Cabbage-invertebrate community monitoring

Monitoring of the invertebrate community involved repeated sampling of the same plants throughout the growing season. Per experimental strip, eight cabbage plants were selected equidistantly throughout the strip, excluding the first and last ten meters of each strip. Two cabbage plants were chosen per plant row on each half of the strip length, and within each half, the order of the rows was randomized. As there was only one replicate of Strip_diversity per field and to increase the sample size of Strip at the reference field, we chose to double the sampling effort in these strips. In the monoculture, we sampled cabbage plants in a similar fashion as in the strip treatments, leaving four plant rows free between rows in which we took samples, creating a similar distance as between samples of different strips within the strip treatments. See [Table S3](#) for a dissemination of the number of replications.

Invertebrates on the selected cabbage plants were counted in 3 to 4 rounds per location per year, which were roughly four weeks apart. The first two of these rounds were considered early season, from June 8th to August 5th; the final two rounds were considered late season, from August 10th to September 28th. After these sampling rounds, the selected cabbage plants were harvested for yield and damage assessment (see below). During monitoring, all invertebrates on the cabbage were identified to the lowest taxonomical unit possible, without having to remove the invertebrates, and counted. In addition to monitoring herbivore communities, we measured two variables related to plant size. The diameter of the plant was measured using measuring tape as the greatest distance between two leaf tips on a plant, and the number of leaves was counted.

2.6 | Cabbage yield and damage assessment

All sampled cabbage plants were harvested in one operation per location per year and stored in a cooler until fresh harvestable weight and damage assessment. Sampled cabbage harvest happened shortly before the first strip level harvest (organic cabbage harvest usually happens manually in two or three rounds). Cabbage heads were separated from the wrapper leaves and stalk, and inspected for any chewing herbivore injury using the protocol of Juventia et al. (2021). Injured head leaves were peeled off until no injury was visible anymore. The wrapper leaves, damaged head leaves and the clean head were weighted separately. Fresh harvestable weight was measured as the total fresh weight of the cabbage head, including injured head leaves. We did not assess marketable yield (the fresh weight after removal of injured leaves) as we believe that the total fresh weight of the cabbage head gives a better indication of how consumptive behaviour of herbivores throughout the season affected eventual crop biomass. Such marketable yield would be mostly influenced by the removal of injured leaves caused by late-season herbivory. We considered damage as the proportion of the total cabbage head fresh weight that we removed due to injury and denote this variable as proportion damaged head weight. Taking the ratio avoids an inherent correlation between total cabbage head weight and the weight of the injured leaves, as heavier cabbage heads also have heavier leaves.

2.7 | Statistics

All statistical analyses were done in R, version 4.2.2.

We used generalized linear models using the *glmmTMB* package (Brooks et al., 2017) to assess the effect of cropping systems on (1) cabbage head fresh weight, (2) proportion damaged head weight, (3) total abundance and richness of early and late herbivores, and (4) abundances of early and late herbivore groups. For all response variables, we used cropping system treatment, placement within the

strip (whether the cabbage was placed in the edge or centre rows), location and year as fixed effects. We used field and strip number (a variable with unique values for each strip in which samples were taken) as random effects. We also included all two-way interactions among fixed variables and performed backward selection using Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) to see which of these interactions increased the fit of the model. If taking out an interaction variable reduced the AIC, it was removed from the final model. For cabbage head fresh weight and herbivore richness, we used a Gaussian distribution. For all herbivore abundances, we used a negative binomial distribution. For proportion damaged head weight, the distribution did not fit well with a Gaussian distribution. Therefore, we transformed the proportion to percentage by multiplying the value by 100 and then rounded the value up to the nearest integer. This data transformation allowed us to fit a model with a negative binomial distribution. Because a large portion of heads was undamaged, we encountered zero-inflation in the data, for which we used zero-inflated models using the 'ziformula' function within *glmmTMB*. We tested for overdispersion (for negative binomial models) and normality of residuals (for Gaussian models) using the 'testResiduals' function of the *dHARMA* package (Hartig, 2018).

To assess the effect of early plant variables and herbivores on the fresh weight of cabbage heads, and to examine how these effects differ among the treatments, we used piecewise structural equation modelling (pSEM), using the 'piecewiseSEM' package (Lefcheck, 2016). We made three models of increasing complexity: (1) model without herbivores (Figure S2a), (2) model with herbivore abundance and richness (Figure S2b), and (3) model with four herbivore groups (Figure S2c) (for more details on the SEM models see text S1). In all pSEM models, we used year and location as fixed factors in all component models. For all three models, we first conceived a model that fit with the hypotheses. Thereafter, we checked the fit of this initial model on the full dataset using Fisher's C. Using a mix of back- and forward selection, we added paths that were vital for the model to fit well using Fisher's C. We similarly checked the fit on subsets for each year, each location, and each cropping system. We removed non-significant paths if removal did not reduce the fit of the model using all data and on any of the subsets. The eventually accepted model was one that fitted with the whole datasets as well as all individual subsets. We tested each component model within the pSEM tested for overdispersion (for negative binomial models) and normality and homogeneity of residuals (for Gaussian models) using the 'testResiduals' function of the *dHARMA* package (Hartig, 2018).

3 | RESULTS

We intensively monitored a total of 1308 cabbage plants throughout the growing season over the course of three years at two experimental field locations (Wageningen and Lelystad). In total, we identified and counted 116,478 herbivorous insects, which consisted of 43% phloem feeders (mainly the aphid *Brevicoryne brassicae* and whiteflies

FIGURE 2 The effect of cropping system and plant size variables on fresh weight of the cabbage head. The overall effect of cropping system on fresh weight of the whole cabbage head (A) and the proportion of fresh weight lost through removal of leaves injured by chewing herbivores (damage) (B), averaged across locations and years. Colours indicate different cropping systems. Compact letter display was used to indicate significant pairwise differences (Tukey HSD, $p < 0.05$) between cropping systems, whereas 'n.s.' indicates no significant effect among cropping systems. The squares indicate estimated means; the vertical lines show the 95% confidence interval. (C) Structural equation model (SEM) fitted on the full data set. Standardized parameter estimates are given on each arrow and arrow width indicates the size of the standardized parameter estimates. Green squares indicate plant variables related to plant size and the blue square indicates the plant variable related to crop yield. (D) Total standardized effect of the three predictor variables on fresh weight of the whole cabbage head, per cropping system. Cabbage plants were grown in five treatments (Figure 1). The colour gradient indicates the size and sign of the effect. A separation in direct and indirect effects of variables on fresh weight head are given in Table S4.

(Aleyrodidae), 26% leaf chewing insects (mainly the lepidopterans *Plutella xylostella* and *Pieris rapae*), 20% thrips (Thysanoptera) and 11% flea beetles (*Phyllotreta atra* and *P. undulata*). For a full list of herbivores see Table S2. Slugs and snails (Gastropoda) were also observed, but their abundances were closely linked to the time of observation, since these are mostly active at night and early in the morning. Therefore, we excluded slugs and snails from the analyses.

3.1 | Cabbage yield and damage

Overall, cabbage plants grown in strip cropping with six crops had a higher yield than those grown in the other, less-diverse cropping systems (Figure 2A). However, yield did not significantly differ between the four treatments with three or less crops, including the monoculture (Figure 2A). Overall, the cropping system had no effect

FIGURE 3 The effect of herbivore abundance and richness on fresh weight and damage of the cabbage head. (A, B) Overall effect of cropping system on late herbivore abundance (B) and richness (C), averaged across locations and years. Colours indicate different cropping systems. Compact letter display was used to indicate significant pairwise differences (Tukey HSD, $p < 0.05$) between cropping systems, whereas 'n.s.' indicates no significant effect among cropping systems. The squares indicate estimated means; the vertical lines show the 95% confidence interval. (C) Total standardized effect of the predictor variables on fresh weight of the whole cabbage head per cropping system. Cabbage plants were grown in five treatments (Figure 1). The colour gradient indicates the size and sign of the effect. A separation in direct and indirect effects of variables on fresh weight head and proportion damaged head weight are given in Tables S5 and S6. (D) Structural equation model (SEM) fitted on the full data set. Standardized parameter estimates are given on each arrow and arrow width also indicates the size of the standardized parameter estimates. Double headed arrows represent relations for which we could not presume a biologically meaningful causal relation, and which were included by their correlated error structure. Green squares indicate plant variables related to plant growth, yellow squares indicate herbivore variables and blue squares indicate plant variables related to crop quantity and quality.

on the proportion of cabbage head weight removed due to herbivore injury, that is on damage (Figure 2B).

3.2 | Herbivore abundance and richness

Insect herbivore abundance tended to be higher in treatments with more than two crops or with two cultivars than in monocultures (Figure 3A). Herbivore richness was higher in the treatment with six crops compared to any of the other crop treatments (Figure 3B).

3.3 | Mixing cultivars, but not crops, reduces the predictability of fresh harvestable weight from early-season plant size

First, we examined how well plant size before and during cabbage head formation predicts fresh harvestable weight and how cropping systems alter these predictions (Figure 2C,D, Figure S3). Early plant size had a strong positive indirect effect on fresh harvestable weight via increasing late plant size, but also a direct positive effect on fresh harvestable weight. This direct positive effect suggests that large plant size early in the season also positively affects harvestable weight irrespective of its effect on above-ground plant growth, for example by reducing herbivore abundances during crop development. The effect of early plant size on fresh harvestable weight was consistent for all treatments, except for the strip treatment with two cabbage cultivars (Strip_cultivar). Here, the positive effect of early plant diameter on fresh harvestable weight was lower than in other treatments, and there was a distinct negative effect of increased early number of leaves. These results show that the addition of a second cultivar within the cropping system reduces how well early plant size predicts crop yield, an effect that seems to be alleviated by including a higher diversity of crops.

3.4 | Herbivores differently affect fresh harvestable weight depending on the cropping system

Next, we examined how plant size and herbivore abundance and richness at two plant developmental stages affected fresh harvestable weight and damage (Figure 3A, Figures S4 and S5, Tables S5 and S6).

Early plant size correlated positively with early, but negatively with late herbivore abundance and richness. Changes in herbivore abundances and richness did not lead to changes in yield and damage in all treatments, except for strip cropping with two cultivars (Strip_cultivar). Here, higher late herbivore abundance reduced fresh harvestable weight and increased damage, whereas late herbivore richness had a positive effect on fresh harvestable weight. Interestingly, in both the simplest strip treatment (Strip) and the treatment that included legumes (Strip_additive), greater damage was associated with greater fresh harvestable weight. These results show that herbivore abundance does not consistently correlate with negative effects on fresh harvestable weight and damage. Also, we found that cropping system treatments alter the strength and sign of the specific effects of herbivores on crop quantity and quality, especially when the treatment included two cultivars.

3.5 | Herbivore groups affect crop yield differently among cropping systems

Lastly, we examined how plant size and the abundance of four herbivore groups before and during cabbage head formation affected fresh harvestable weight and damage, and how these effects varied among cropping systems (Figure 4, Figures S6 and S7, Tables S7 and S8). Early plant size correlated positively with early abundance of most herbivore groups, but the herbivores had mostly low correlations with late plant size, yield or damage.

However, specific herbivores had treatment-specific effects on fresh harvestable weight and damage. In the monoculture, late-season thrips abundance negatively correlated with fresh harvestable weight, whereas late-season flea beetle abundance correlated positively. In the simplest strip treatment (Strip) and in the simplest treatment with two cultivars (Strip_cultivar) early-season leaf chews abundance was negatively correlated with yield. Also, in both treatments that included two cultivars (Strip_cultivar and Strip_diversity) high abundances of early-season chews were associated with lower damage at the time of harvest. In the simplest treatment with two cabbage cultivars (Strip_cultivar) late-season thrips abundance was associated with reduced fresh harvestable weight. In the treatment with legumes (Strip_additive), late-season leaf chews abundance negatively affected fresh harvestable weight, whereas a higher abundance of flea beetles late in the season was associated with higher fresh harvestable weight.

FIGURE 4 The effect of herbivore groups on fresh weight of the cabbage head. (a) Structural equation model (SEM) fitted on the full data set. Standardized parameter estimates are given on each arrow and arrow width also indicates the size of the standardized parameter estimates. Double headed arrows represent relations for which we could not presume a biologically meaningful causal relation, and which were included by their correlated error structure. Green squares indicate plant variables related to plant growth, yellow squares indicate herbivore variables and blue squares indicate plant variables related to crop quantity and quality. (b) Total standardized effect of the predictor variables on fresh weight of the whole cabbage head per cropping system. Cabbage plants were grown in five treatments (Figure 1). The colour gradient indicates the size and sign of the effect. A separation in direct and indirect effects of variables on fresh weight head and proportion damaged head weight are given in Tables S7 and S8.

These results show that (1) different herbivore groups have different effects on crop yield and damage, (2) the effects of specific herbivores differ depending on the time of arrival and the cropping system, (3) early-season herbivores only have minor effects on plant growth, and (4) early-season herbivores can have stronger effects on crop damage than late herbivores, despite not being present whilst the harvestable plant parts are growing.

4 | DISCUSSION

Cropping systems alter how herbivores affect crop yield, as simply looking at the abundance of herbivores as a proxy for pest control foregoes differences in survival of and injury by herbivores. Our results show minor effects of cropping systems on herbivore abundances, but herbivores did show distinct cropping system-dependent effects on fresh harvestable weight. For example, the most diverse strip treatment (Strip_diversity) had the heaviest cabbage heads, whilst also having the highest abundance of herbivores. These seemingly contrasting results fit with previous findings in the most diverse strip treatment in the same experimental fields in which, despite higher egg abundances, the survival of a specialist cabbage herbivore (*Delia radicum*) was lower (Karssemeijer et al., 2024), abundance and richness of both ground-dwelling and aerial predators were higher (Croijmans et al., in press; Cuperus et al., 2023) and parasitism by a natural enemy of a specialist cabbage herbivore (*Pieris brassicae*) was higher (Croijmans et al., 2024). As a result, fewer adult herbivores of cabbage (Cuperus et al., 2023), lower foliar injury (Juventia et al., 2021) and more injury-free product were observed in more diverse cropping systems (Carrillo-Reche et al., 2023), although this did not translate into a significant increase in yield (Carrillo-Reche et al., 2023; Ditzler et al., 2023). The increase in fresh harvestable weight in the most diverse strip-cropping system might thus not be caused by a reduction in the abundance of herbivores compared to less-diverse cropping systems, but by other biotic or abiotic factors. Nitrogen availability under different fertilization regimes (Han et al., 2022), competition or niche complementarity among crop species (Bourke et al., 2021), changes in arable flora (Kremen & Miles, 2012), soil microbial communities under different crop rotations (Viketoft et al., 2021), belowground herbivores (Karssemeijer et al., 2024), top-down regulation of herbivore communities by naturally occurring predators (Croijmans et al., 2024; Rakotomalala et al., 2023) and disease prevalence (Ditzler et al., 2021) are all factors that may alter plant growth and which were not measured in

this study. Our results indicate that strip-cropping systems facilitate beneficial interactions that allow herbivores to coexist on crops without causing economic damage, whilst simultaneously increasing crop yield.

Early plant size was a good predictor of fresh harvestable weight in most cropping systems, but inclusion of two cultivars within the system reduced the strength of this prediction. Cabbage is known as a bad competitor early in the season, and cropping systems where companion plants are planted or sown before cabbages reduce cabbage yields (Carrillo-Reche et al., 2023). Our results reinforce that early plant growth is vital for crop yield. Cropping systems designed to enhance cabbage productivity should aim to avoid competition or damage to freshly planted cabbage plants, whereas negative trade-offs for cabbage can be accepted later in the season. In cultivar mixtures, plant growth might be more unpredictable as it also depends on the cultivar composition of the neighbouring plants, which changes competitive interactions compared to a cropping system with only one cultivar (Bourke et al., 2021). Moreover, although we mostly did not observe higher herbivore abundances in this cropping system, we did observe the strongest negative effects of herbivores on fresh harvestable weight in the cropping system with two cultivars. Both leaf chewers and thrips negatively affected fresh harvestable weight, but chewers did so only early and thrips only late in the season. For thrips, this difference between early and late abundance might be due to thrips only reaching damage thresholds late in the season during an observed outbreak. These observations might indicate that our choice for a cultivar that is attractive to both herbivores and their natural enemies (Poelman, Dam, et al., 2009; Poelman, Oduor, et al., 2009) might have backfired. We expected this cultivar to serve as a trap crop that would facilitate beneficial tri-trophic interactions by bringing herbivores and natural enemies together. However, this might also reduce the chance that natural enemies would visit the cash cultivar when herbivores still end up there, and this is reinforced by non-host herbivores that can also increase parasitoid recruitment by the attractive cultivar (Croijmans et al., 2022). In the most diverse strip-cropping system (Strip_diversity), which also included both cultivars, this reduction in predation might be mediated by increased predation facilitated by the higher crop diversity (Croijmans et al., 2024). Thus, the attractive cultivar might interfere with biological control by naturally occurring natural enemies on the cash cultivar, which would risk a negative effect on yield. This higher risk of herbivore damage comes on top of a reduction in yield due to the replacement of 1/8th of the cabbages by the attractive, unmarketable cultivar. Any crop management choice will have its own suite

of alterations to herbivore-mediated effects on crop yield, which we need to understand better if we are to design cropping systems that enhance pest control. Validation of the SEMs with independently collected data would confirm the suitability of the causal model as a tool for real-world predictions and the generalization of the findings.

Chewer abundance early in the season reduced crop damage in the simplest strip-cropping system (Strip) and strip cropping with two cabbage cultivars (Strip_cultivar), partly through decreased late-season abundances of chewers and flea beetles. Potentially, the presence of early-season herbivores not only reduced the abundance of late-season herbivores, but also their performance or survival (Ohgushi, 2005). Early-season herbivores affect the herbivore community via plant-mediated interactions, which have cascading effects on crop yield and quality (Poelman et al., 2023). Herbivory can change secondary metabolites, which alter attraction or apparency of the host plant to later herbivores and their natural enemies (Croijmans et al., 2022; Van Zandt & Agrawal, 2004). Furthermore, herbivores can affect the performance of later herbivores through complementary or antagonistic defensive pathways (Mertens et al., 2021). Such plant-mediated effects of early herbivores on later herbivore presence and performance can have cascading effects on yield and especially on crop quality (Stam et al., 2014). These indirect, community-driven effects on crop yield are complex by nature, but necessary to understand when designing ecology-based alternatives to intensive agriculture.

Throughout the value chain from farm to fork, we might be too worried about insect herbivores and the crop injury they cause for three key reasons. Firstly, herbivores had mostly minor effects on crop yield, despite not using any pesticides. Non-target effects of pesticides can reduce the abundance of natural enemies (Hallmann et al., 2014). Even targeted pesticide applications, including those in integrated pest management strategies, interfere with prey-predator cycles (Janssen & Van Rijn, 2021; Keasar et al., 2023) and, in doing so, ignore the largely unknown effects of environmental context on herbivore-crop interactions, as we showed in this study. New approaches that include natural enemies (Keasar et al., 2023) reveal greater acknowledgment of the potential of cropping systems to self-regulate damage levels below economic thresholds. Secondly, for leafy vegetables like white cabbage, marketable yield can be increased by breaking false notions of product quality (Dara, 2019). In our study, the biggest losses in crop biomass were generated by the removal of leaves slightly injured by herbivores, not by the injury caused by the herbivores themselves. Thirdly, herbivores play an integral role in food webs, and their structural removal in agricultural systems is a bottom-up cause of the loss of (insect) biodiversity (Beaumelle et al., 2023; Vidal & Murphy, 2018). Our work shows that, using agroecological management, there is potential for sharing our crops with insect herbivores without incurring major losses in yield.

Agriculture finds itself at the crossroads of continuing curative measures against herbivorous pests or adopting more ecological approaches to maintaining crop yield. Many preventative measures are no longer societally accepted, but farmers, their collectives

and governments are still hesitant towards phasing out pesticides (Bakker et al., 2021). Diversification of crops by strip cropping offers strong potential to control insect herbivores via ecological processes. Such ecological solutions to agricultural problems need an ecological mindset that considers the complexities of plant responses and herbivore communities. Future academic research should focus on unravelling the mechanisms underlying these complexities. For the short term, our work shows that crop diversification reduces the impact of herbivory and increases crop yield, all whilst being manageable under current, organic farming practices.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Luuk Croijmans: conceptualization, methodology, formal analysis, investigation, data curation, writing—original draft, writing—review & editing, visualization, supervision. Daan Mertens: conceptualization, methodology, formal analysis, writing—review & editing. Dirk F. van Apeldoorn: conceptualization, writing—review & editing, visualization, supervision, project administration, funding acquisition. Yufei Jia: investigation, data curation. Nelson Ríos Hernández: investigation. Erik H. Poelman: conceptualization, methodology, writing—original draft, writing—review & editing, supervision, project administration, funding acquisition.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the work reported in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data and scripts are publicly available from 4TU.ResearchData via the following DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4121/2136d072-c111-48e0-8136-7e76f8f3f27c> (Croijmans et al., 2025).

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REFERENCES

- Aguilera, G., Riggi, L., Miller, K., Roslin, T., & Bommarco, R. (2021). Organic fertilisation enhances generalist predators and suppresses aphid growth in the absence of specialist predators. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 58(7), 1455–1465. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.13862>
- Bakker, L., Sok, J., van der Werf, W., & Bianchi, F. J. J. A. (2021). Kicking the habit: What makes and breaks farmers' intentions to reduce pesticide use? *Ecological Economics*, 180, 106868. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2020.106868>
- Barot, S., Allard, V., Cantarel, A., Enjalbert, J., Gauffreteau, A., Goldringer, I., Lata, J.-C., Le Roux, X., Niboyet, A., & Porcher, E. (2017). Designing mixtures of varieties for multifunctional agriculture with the help of ecology. A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 37(2), 13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-017-0418-x>
- Barzman, M., Bärberi, P., Birch, A. N. E., Boonekamp, P., Dachbrodt-Saaydeh, S., Graf, B., Hommel, B., Jensen, J. E., Kiss, J., Kudsk, P., Lamichhane, J. R., Messéan, A., Moonen, A.-C., Ratnadass, A., Ricci, P., Sarah, J.-L., & Sattin, M. (2015). Eight principles of integrated pest management. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 35(4), 1199–1215. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-015-0327-9>
- Beaumelle, L., Tison, L., Eisenhauer, N., Hines, J., Malladi, S., Pelosi, C., Thouvenot, L., & Phillips, H. R. P. (2023). Pesticide effects on soil fauna communities—A meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 60(7), 1239–1253. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.14437>
- Beillouin, D., Ben-Ari, T., Malézieux, E., Seufert, V., & Makowski, D. (2021). Positive but variable effects of crop diversification on biodiversity and ecosystem services. *Global Change Biology*, 27(19), 4697–4710. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15747>
- Boege, K., & Marquis, R. J. (2005). Facing herbivory as you grow up: The ontogeny of resistance in plants. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 20(8), 441–448. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2005.05.001>
- Bourke, P. M., Evers, J. B., Bijma, P., van Apeldoorn, D. F., Smulders, M. J. M., Kuyper, T. W., Mommer, L., & Bonnema, G. (2021). Breeding beyond monoculture: Putting the “intercrop” into crops. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 12, 734167. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2021.734167>
- Brooks, M. E., Kristensen, K., van Benthem, K. J., Magnusson, A., Berg, C. W., Nielsen, A., Skaug, H. J., Mächler, M., & Bolker, B. M. (2017). glmmTMB balances speed and flexibility among packages for zero-inflated generalized linear mixed modeling. *The R Journal*, 9(2), 378–400.
- Carrillo-Reche, J., Le Noc, T., van Apeldoorn, D. F., Juventia, S. D., Westhoek, A., Shanmugam, S., Kristensen, H. L., Hondebrink, M., Himanen, S. J., Kivijärvi, P., Lepse, L., Dane, S., & Rossing, W. A. H. (2023). Finding guidelines for cabbage intercropping systems design as a first step in a meta-analysis relay for vegetables. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 354, 108564. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2023.108564>
- Croijmans, L., Cuperus, F., van Apeldoorn, D. F., Bianchi, F. J. J. A., Rossing, W. A. H., & Poelman, E. H. (in press). Strip cropping in organic agriculture results in 15% higher ground beetle richness and 30% higher activity density than monocultures. *eLife*, <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.11.02.621655>
- Croijmans, L., Mertens, D., van Apeldoorn, D. F., Jia, Y., Ríos Hernández, N., & Poelman, E. H. (2025). Data underlying the publication: Herbivore prevalence poorly predicts yield in diverse cropping systems. 4TU.ResearchData, <https://doi.org/10.4121/96110176-80c7-4ba9-9cf8-87f188e1fa65>
- Croijmans, L., Valstar, R. T., Schuur, L., Jacobs, I., van Apeldoorn, D. F., & Poelman, E. H. (2022). Intraspecific plant variation and nonhost herbivores affect parasitoid host location behaviour. *Animal Behaviour*, 194, 169–184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anbehav.2022.09.021>
- Croijmans, L., van Apeldoorn, D. F., Sanfilippo, F., Zangpo, T., & Poelman, E. H. (2024). Crop species diversity levels with attract and reward strategies to enhance *Pieris brassicae* parasitism rate by *Cotesia glomerata* in strip intercropping. *Functional Ecology*, 38(3), 654–667. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2435.14502>
- Cuny, M. A. C., Gendry, J., Hernández-Cumplido, J., & Benrey, B. (2018). Changes in plant growth and seed production in wild lima bean in response to herbivory are attenuated by parasitoids. *Oecologia*, 187(2), 447–457. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00442-018-4119-1>
- Cuperus, F., Ozinga, W. A., Bianchi, F. J. J. A., Croijmans, L., Rossing, W. A. H., & van Apeldoorn, D. F. (2023). Effects of field-level strip and mixed cropping on aerial arthropod and arable flora communities. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 354, 108568. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2023.108568>
- Dara, S. K. (2019). The new integrated Pest management paradigm for the modern age. *Journal of Integrated Pest Management*, 10(1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jipm/pmz010>
- Ditzler, L., van Apeldoorn, D. F., Schulte, R. P. O., Tiftonell, P., & Rossing, W. A. H. (2021). Redefining the field to mobilize three-dimensional diversity and ecosystem services on the arable farm. *European Journal of Agronomy*, 122, 126197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eja.2020.126197>
- Ditzler, L., Rossing, W. A. H., Schulte, R. P. O., Hageman, J., & van Apeldoorn, D. F. (2023). Prospects for increasing the resolution of crop diversity for agroecosystem service delivery in a Dutch arable system. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 351, 108472. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2023.108472>
- European Commission. (2020). *A farm to fork strategy for a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system*. COM 381 final. European Commission. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0381>
- García, L. C., & Eubanks, M. D. (2019). Overcompensation for insect herbivory: A review and meta-analysis of the evidence. *Ecology*, 100(3), e02585. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ecy.2585>
- Hallmann, C. A., Foppen, R. P. B., van Turnhout, C. A. M., de Kroon, H., & Jongejans, E. (2014). Declines in insectivorous birds are associated with high neonicotinoid concentrations. *Nature*, 511(7509), 341–343. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature13531>
- Han, P., Lavoie, A.-V., Rodriguez-Saona, C., & Desneux, N. (2022). Bottom-up forces in agroecosystems and their potential impact on arthropod pest management. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 67(1), 239–259. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ento-060121-060505>

- Hartig, F. (2018). DHARMA: Residual diagnostics for hierarchical (multi-level/mixed) regression models. In *R Packag version 020*. <https://cir.nii.ac.jp/crid/1370580229833186830>
- Janssen, A., & van Rijn, P. C. J. (2021). Pesticides do not significantly reduce arthropod pest densities in the presence of natural enemies. *Ecology Letters*, 24(9), 2010–2024. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.13819>
- Jensen, E. S., Peoples, M. B., & Hauggaard-Nielsen, H. (2010). Faba bean in cropping systems. *Field Crops Research*, 115(3), 203–216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2009.10.008>
- Juventia, S. D., Rossing, W. A. H., Ditzler, L., & van Apeldoorn, D. F. (2021). Spatial and genetic crop diversity support ecosystem service delivery: A case of yield and biocontrol in Dutch organic cabbage production. *Field Crops Research*, 261, 108015. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2020.108015>
- Karssemeijer, P. N., Croijmans, L., Gajendiran, K., Gols, R., van Apeldoorn, D. F., van Loon, J. J. A., Dicke, M., & Poelman, E. H. (2024). Diverse cropping systems lead to higher larval mortality of the cabbage root fly (*Delia radicum*). *Journal of Pest Science*, 97(1), 337–353. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10340-023-01629-1>
- Keasar, T., Wajnberg, E., Heimpel, G., Hardy, I. C. W., Harpaz, L. S., Gottlieb, D., & van Nouhuys, S. (2023). Dynamic economic thresholds for insecticide applications against agricultural pests: Importance of pest and natural enemy migration. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 116(2), 321–330. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/toad019>
- Kremen, C., & Miles, A. (2012). Ecosystem services in biologically diversified versus conventional farming systems: Benefits, externalities, and trade-offs. *Ecology and Society*, 17(4), art40. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-05035-170440>
- Lefcheck, J. S. (2016). piecewiseSEM: Piecewise structural equation modelling in r for ecology, evolution, and systematics. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 7(5), 573–579. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12512>
- Letourneau, D. K., Armbrrecht, I., Rivera, B. S., Lerma, J. M., Carmona, E. J., Daza, M. C., Escobar, S., Galindo, V., Gutiérrez, C., López, S. D., Mejía, J. L., Rangel, A. M. A., Rangel, J. H., Rivera, L., Saavedra, C. A., Torres, A. M., & Trujillo, A. R. (2011). Does plant diversity benefit agroecosystems? A synthetic review. *Ecological Applications*, 21(1), 9–21. <https://doi.org/10.1890/09-2026.1>
- Mansion-Vaquíé, A., Ferrer, A., Ramon-Portugal, F., Wezel, A., & Magro, A. (2020). Intercropping impacts the host location behaviour and population growth of aphids. *Entomologia Experimentalis et Applicata*, 168(1), 41–52. <https://doi.org/10.1111/eea.12848>
- Mertens, D., Fernández De Bobadilla, M., Rusman, Q., Bloem, J., Douma, J. C., & Poelman, E. H. (2021). Plant defence to sequential attack is adapted to prevalent herbivores. *Nature Plants*, 7(10), 1347–1353. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41477-021-00999-7>
- Ohgushi, T. (2005). Indirect interaction webs: Herbivore-induced effects through trait change in plants. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics*, 36(1), 81–105. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ecolsys.36.091704.175523>
- Poelman, E. H., Bourne, M. E., Croijmans, L., Cuny, M. A. C., Delamore, Z., Joachim, G., Kalisvaart, S. N., Kamps, B. B. J., Longuemare, M., Suijkerbuijk, H. A. C., & Zhang, N. X. (2023). Bringing fundamental insights of induced resistance to agricultural management of herbivore pests. *Journal of Chemical Ecology*, 49(5–6), 218–229. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10886-023-01432-3>
- Poelman, E. H., Dam, N. M., van Loon, J. J. A., Vet, L. E. M., & Dicke, M. (2009). Chemical diversity in Brassica oleracea affects biodiversity of insect herbivores. *Ecology*, 90(7), 1863–1877. <https://doi.org/10.1890/08-0977.1>
- Poelman, E. H., Oduor, A. M. O., Broekgaarden, C., Hordijk, C. A., Jansen, J. J., van Loon, J. J. A., Dam, N. M., Vet, L. E. M., & Dicke, M. (2009). Field parasitism rates of caterpillars on Brassica oleracea plants are reliably predicted by differential attraction of Cotesia parasitoids. *Functional Ecology*, 23(5), 951–962. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2435.2009.01570.x>
- Poveda, K., Gómez, M. I., & Martínez, E. (2008). Diversification practices: Their effect on pest regulation and production. *Revista Colombiana de Entomología*, 34(2), 131–144.
- Poveda, K., Jiménez, M. I. G., & Kessler, A. (2010). The enemy as ally: Herbivore-induced increase in crop yield. *Ecological Applications*, 20(7), 1787–1793. <https://doi.org/10.1890/09-1726.1>
- Rakotomalala, A. A. N. A., Ficiyan, A. M., & Tschantke, T. (2023). Intercropping enhances beneficial arthropods and controls pests: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 356, 108617. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2023.108617>
- Reiss, E. R., & Drinkwater, L. E. (2018). Cultivar mixtures: A meta-analysis of the effect of intraspecific diversity on crop yield. *Ecological Applications*, 28(1), 62–77. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.1629>
- Stam, J. M., Kroes, A., Li, Y., Gols, R., van Loon, J. J. A., Poelman, E. H., & Dicke, M. (2014). Plant interactions with multiple insect herbivores: From community to genes. *Annual Review of Plant Biology*, 65(1), 689–713. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-arplant-050213-035937>
- Tamburini, G., Bommarco, R., Wanger, T. C., Kremen, C., van der Heijden, M. G. A., Liebman, M., & Hallin, S. (2020). Agricultural diversification promotes multiple ecosystem services without compromising yield. *Science Advances*, 6(45), eaba1715. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aba1715>
- Tooker, J. F., & Frank, S. D. (2012). Genotypically diverse cultivar mixtures for insect pest management and increased crop yields. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 49(5), 974–985. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2012.02173.x>
- van Zandt, P. A., & Agrawal, A. A. (2004). Community-wide impacts of herbivore-induced plant responses in milkweed (*Asclepias syriaca*). *Ecology*, 85(9), 2616–2629. <https://doi.org/10.1890/03-0622>
- Vidal, M. C., & Murphy, S. M. (2018). Bottom-up vs. top-down effects on terrestrial insect herbivores: A meta-analysis. *Ecology Letters*, 21(1), 138–150. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12874>
- Viketoft, M., Riggi, L. G. A., Bommarco, R., Hallin, S., & Taylor, A. R. (2021). Type of organic fertilizer rather than organic amendment per se increases abundance of soil biota. *PeerJ*, 9, e11204. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.11204>
- Wagner, D. L., Grames, E. M., Forister, M. L., Berenbaum, M. R., & Stopak, D. (2021). Insect decline in the Anthropocene: Death by a thousand cuts. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 118(2), e2023989118. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2023989118>
- Züst, T., & Agrawal, A. A. (2017). Trade-offs between plant growth and defense against insect herbivory: An emerging mechanistic synthesis. *Annual Review of Plant Biology*, 68(1), 513–534. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-arplant-042916-040856>

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

Figure S1. Maps of field lay-out of Wageningen (a–c) and Lelystad (d–f) per year.

Figure S2. Hypothesized effects of plant size and herbivore variables on damage and fresh weight of the cabbage head.

Figure S3. Comparison of pSEM models without herbivores per cropping system treatment.

Figure S4. The effect of herbivore abundance and richness on damage of the cabbage head.

Figure S5. Comparison of pSEM models with herbivore abundance and richness per crop configuration.

Figure S6. The effect of herbivore groups on damage of the cabbage head.

Figure S7. Comparison of pSEM models with herbivore groups per treatment.

Table S1. Checklist of all flora included in some form in this study.

Table S2. Checklist of all herbivores included in this study.

Table S3. Number of replications per location and year.

Table S4. Effect of early and late season plant size on fresh weight of the cabbage head, per cropping design.

Table S5. Effects of early and late season plant size, herbivore abundance and richness, and cabbage head damage on fresh weight of the cabbage head, per cropping design.

Table S6. Effects of early and late season plant size and herbivore abundance and richness on proportion damaged head weight, per cropping design.

Table S7. Effects of early and late season plant size, abundances of herbivore classes, and cabbage head damage on fresh weight of the

cabbage head, per cropping design. Both direct and indirect effects of early and late plant size variables are shown.

Table S8. Effects of early and late season plant size and abundances of herbivore classes on proportion damaged head weight, per cropping design.

Text S1. Additional information on SEM models.

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